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SUMMARY KEYWORDS

clapping, string, happy, moving, kids, vibrations, interpreted, thought, teachers, playing, feel, spinning, bite, interacting, floor, tired, super, lights

SPEAKERS

Interviewer, Observer 1

Interviewer 00:00

Don't feel pressured to answer my question if you actually part of the thing, if you don't feel like it can stop up at any time, that would be better

Observer 1 00:08

Maybe [Observer 2] is going to get into a super connected feeling mode if I deliver, maybe you

Interviewer 00:15

Perhaps, maybe not. We don't know.

Observer 1 00:18

Yeah.

Interviewer 00:19

So okay, we'll start with this micro phenomenological interview. This kind of interviews a little bit different to the interviews that we performed like, normally, because in the interviews we perform normally, we have like pre scripted questions, in this case, it's going to be open. And we'll ask you to focus on one specific minute to where the kids were interacting that you found interesting, or meaningful, okay, doesn't need to be anything long, actually, we will explore a short experience has a commencement and an end. So what we do through this interview method is with zoom in, like putting the experience into a microscope. So what's going to happen is that I'll ask you how things were, I might get repetitive at some point and I might ask you like several times I go, but how was it... really. And the other thing is that as you are telling me things like how was the experience, I will be doing a brief recap. So go back and repeat to you what you have said, in case you find that my description is not accurate. Feel free to interrupt me correct me and say, Okay, this is not the word that I said, or this is not really what I meant, because sometimes we say things and then it's like, we sort of go back and adjust

Observer 1 01:37

or Yeah, especially in not native language. Yeah, it happens a lot. So actually, Marie was using the dictionary. Yeah. And it has happened before. Feel free if you find like a word that is "grrr" yes, I want to say that, but I don't know in English I'm not 100% sure just check the dictionary. I have had that before. Even I do that I was super useful for actually to be part of the interview also for her master's thesis.

Interviewer 02:06

I think so. Yeah. I think so I have noticed that she kind of learns, made her reflect on things. So okay, of course, if you feel tired, feel free to like say, okay, like, can we stop here and stop at any time? Okay, I will ask you questions that are not directed to what you're saying. Okay. So I will ask you if you agree, just to pick a moment that you found interesting. Yeah. And just describe to me like, briefly, like lightly...

Observer 1 02:48

So yeah, I'm thinking about a couple of moments that were actually interesting. So

Interviewer 02:54

You might want to describe both, and perhaps we can pick one.

Observer 1 02:57

Yeah. There's one that I know the [Observer 2] you saw. And notice, and that's why he made me notice it too, because I didn't see it. So maybe he wants to talk about that one. Um, let me think if there are any more. Okay, guess the ones that I remember the strongest is there was one, there was a kid that was on the big platform in the middle. And he came. And in the beginning, even before we started the experiments, he was already playing on the string. Super happy laughing. And I don't remember if he was clapping his hands then or if he did it later, but he was already from the start, just like he was just in there, doing his thing starting off, even before the experiment has started. And then later during the session, he put his head like this, and he picked the string. And he tried to do that several times. So that's one thing that I remember, because I think just what I interpreted was that he was enjoying himself. And the other thing that I noticed when [Observer 2] told me was that when I was observing in the end, I think this was the last session when we had they were on the floor. And they were all pretty tired. So it was clear that the last two, the girl in the corner that was further away from you, she was hungry and tired. I think because she usually has a snack that time or something like that. And we were discussing that. But then the other guy, the one that had been like super, super exciting the beginning who bit the string, he was on moving so much... or not at all almost, but his platform was very strong. So he was vibrating very, a lot. And then there was this other guy who was moving around a lot in the room and also spinning. And he was suddenly coming closer to that platform. And [Observer 2], you said whispered to me, he's going closer to that guy's platform, because he wants to feel the vibrations. So that was his interpretation. So maybe he wants to talk about that. But I was also observing that child a lot, because he was moving a lot. And he was very sociable. And he was lying down a lot on the floor. And he was, you know, he, we had eye contact, we talked a little bit. And he seemed very happy all the time. Even in the very end, when everyone was tired, and like, almost sleeping on the floor he was just spinning. So I guess those are the two that I remember the most or clearly that they had a good time. Because the other two was a bit more difficult for me to interpret what was going on, because they were not moving as much. And they were not playing themselves so much. Yeah. Yeah.

Interviewer 06:24

Okay, so we have two moments here. So the first one was one of them. One of the boys that when he arrived, and he was really seems to be happy. He was like, doing his its own thing. He was already playing with the string even before the experience started. At some point, he was lying on the floor, actually, to feel that what you said to feel like the the vibrations of the string, or was he like?

Observer 1 06:51

So he was actually, the interesting thing about him was that he was so excited in the beginning when he was down on the floor, and he had haptics, he didn't move a lot. And he was quiet. And my interpretation was that he's tired.

Interviewer 07:08

Okay.

Observer 1 07:09

So whereas the other kids, the one that came to his platform, and moved, and was spinning around, he was just super excited all the time. Yeah, from what I remember, but then if I would look at the videos, probably I would see that there's a difference between the sessions.

Interviewer 07:26

It seems that there was a moment... Okay, so let me clarify, too, because these moments like seem to be sort of mixed between them. So it was like... this boy, that was happy in the beginning, right. And I playing with the string, but then when the during the last experience, he was like, more like inactive?

Observer 1 07:51

Yes, he didn't do really anything which surprised me.

Interviewer 07:54

Yeah... He was like, they're like static, like, quiet, like, without moving. But this was this other boy who was like really like spinning and he was approaching to. And you also mentioned that this platform was very powerful.

Observer 1 08:08

Yes, because it's the biggest one, the biggest one.

Interviewer 08:10

Okay. But you also mentioned that the guy that was happy the beginning, at some point, he was like, the face was touching the vibrations, I think you said on the floor, but I think that it was like something else. Perhaps I didn't get that right.

Observer 1 08:26

Yeah, maybe... I think what he did was that he... several times he was sitting in the wheelchair. Yeah, he did this. When he I don't know if he did this when he was on the floor. Okay, maybe try them. They tried to stop him. Because I guess, like you shouldn't do that. He was not a way of interacting that we

had thought about. But he was leaning his head so he could bite the string like this. So he's still in the chair. And that he bit it.

Interviewer 08:54

Okay. Oh,

Observer 1 08:56

so maybe that's usually the way of interacting with stuff for him.

Interviewer 09:01

Yeah. Okay.

Observer 1 09:02

Because he seemed to be happy. But he didn't. We didn't appear to me like it was something that was like, out of the ordinary.

Interviewer 09:10

I see... So then he was will go back. So he was happy, right? He was playing with the string, but he was in the wheelchair. And his face was leaning towards like the cord like the string and he was biting the string.

Observer 1 09:25

Yes.

Interviewer 09:25

And the string was making noise, right?

Observer 1 09:28

Yes, yeah. So as soon as he moves the string, I guess they do we missed? Yeah, this I guess I don't remember exactly. If he was biting it to the very extent that he was making sound or if he was biting it and he was not moving. But it was very short. I think it happened at least twice, that he was biting it. And then I remember seeing another time when he tried to bite but the teacher tried to make him stop.

Interviewer 10:01

Okay. And the time when he was happy and playing with string in a way that sounded during the sound, how was he playing with string?

Observer 1 10:14

Quite... physically because they remember that the sounds it was not only one sound, but it was several. Yeah. And in order to get the kind of sound that he has, you have to do it pretty quickly for them to build up, okay to get different pitches. So I think he was moving. I wouldn't say violent, but like a pretty a lot. And he was also if I don't remember wrong laughing and he was clapping his hands quite a lot when he was in the wheelchair. In the beginning, I think this don't really remember, you know,

what of this was like, before everything started or if he was we should have everything on camera in either case.

Interviewer 11:03

Yeah, that's okay. So you said that he was moving at some point, like, kind of violently, like, so it generates is filled up. Which part of his body was he using to like, make the sound specifically.

Observer 1 11:19

So I think he was using one hand could be that he was using two win the strings. So if I try to remember, I'm not super sure if he was doing like this, or if it was more that he was hitting it?

Interviewer 11:40

Yeah, okay. But apparently, he was using his hands. And he was like, also like leaning towards the string and trying to bite it.

Observer 1 11:54

Yeah, to me, it really looks like he was just like, taking a bite, like really do like this had to reach it in a good angle for him. And then he was just stuck and attached to it. Okay. And then sooner or later, someone came to like, remove him, which made me think and he also said that he can't do that, like we should have that... we should have disinfected them before, because I didn't know that they would bite them. Or I didn't think about that. And it also notice now that we just uploaded the video, we just took them from the cameras. And before we put them on harddrive, there was another child, I think, or maybe it was home that had some other kind of bites toy in the string with the rat at the end, so I don't know, maybe this is like they they have bite toys. And the

Interviewer 12:49

it was the guy that was spinning.

Observer 1 12:51

Ah, okay! So maybe it's a it's a way of interacting with things that we haven't really thought about.

Interviewer 13:00

Okay, so let's try to reconstruct then like the chronology of... I know, that's difficult. So, okay. The kids arrived, he was like, really excited, right? It wasn't the... How were the lights were on were off. First, when

Observer 1 13:15

he came, the lights were on. And he was one of the first who came in. And he arrived at the big platform

Interviewer 13:21

at the big platform.

Observer 1 13:23

And the lights were on he was already starting to play alone pretty much without without instructions for [Observer3], because he came in with [Observer3]

Interviewer 13:29

Perfect.

Observer 1 13:30

And the lights are on when he started.

Interviewer 13:32

Okay, so he started playing with the hands apparently.

Observer 1 13:35

Yeah.

Interviewer 13:36

And then he was also like, trays was leaning towards like the cord and was like, trying to find the angle to, like, bite the cord. At some point. The pedagogue, sort of like one of the assistants. Yeah. Took him.

Observer 1 13:54

Yes, but that was way later during the way late. Because it was... it was... it was dark. So it was one during one of the sessions.

Interviewer 14:02

Okay, yeah. So let's focus them on one. He was like actually active and happy and was the lights on. And he was like, sort of playing. And so this bite happened when still like the light was on.

Observer 1 14:16

Not the bite happened when the lights were off.

Interviewer 14:19

Okay.

Observer 1 14:20

So the lights are on in the big gear we're on in the beginning, when for everything start that we were just waiting for, for the two other kids actually. So like I'm rolling in with this girl in the corner, trying to place her where how to put her in the best way and he rolls in behind to the other platform. And before even the other kids have gone into the room. He starts playing.

Interviewer 14:48

There was a moment when you said at the very beginning of this description that this kid that was happy was trying to feel the vibrations

Observer 1 14:59

oh the other kid...

Interviewer 15:00

Which one?

Observer 1 15:03

So the one that was trying to feel the vibrations was the one that was on the platform next to this one that was biting.

Interviewer 15:11

Okay,

Observer 1 15:11

the one on the floor.

Interviewer 15:12

All right. Oh, I see. Okay.

Observer 1 15:15

So that was I didn't really I didn't connect that. But that's how we interpreted the situation, because he was spinning around. And this was the condition when he didn't have any vibrations. And to him, it seemed like he was really approaching that platform because he could feel that the vibrations were coming from there.

Interviewer 15:37

Oh, I see. Okay. So that was close interpretation. Yes. Okay.

Observer 1 15:44

But I also thought a lot about that that child was very active and seem to be enjoying himself and was really happy. Now. Okay. So is actually moving so much in the beginning that his wheelchair almost fell? And I don't know if that was because he was happy or if he was frustrated.

Interviewer 16:07

It's hard to know. Yes. So going back to so the kid that was happy at the beginning and was playing with the cord. And you said that okay, he was like happy and excited. Although it's hard to interpret, how do you know that he was happy?

Observer 1 16:26

Yes. So he was making nonverbal sounds, I think... So he was making some sounds with his voice that made me I guess, just instinctively, I'm like, he's happy. And he was moving a lot. And it feels it looks to me like he was, you know, he was doing things he got a response, he reacted to it. And then he continued based on that. So he Ross's that's how I interpreted it. But then also the hand-clapping was how, one of the things that I like this means I guess I just like, Okay, this must be happy. There also. So sometimes when several kids at the same time, were clapping their hands, and it felt a bit like they had

some kind of moment going on. Being happy all together. That I don't remember. I'm not sure if that was also the other child, the one that was spinning there was also clapping with someone else that was clapping. So that was one moment, and I don't remember exactly when that was that he felt like he was clapping. You know, someone else was clapping.

Interviewer 17:45

Yeah, there was one moment when it seems that they were about to start clapping altogether.

Observer 1 17:52

Yeah, there was some kind of sensation of that they were doing things together.

Interviewer 17:58

How do you feel that they were doing these things together? How do you feel it? How did it how did you feel that? Okay, something is happening.

Observer 1 18:12

I kind of felt that there was some kind of communication in between the people in the room. Like between the children and the teachers, and that they were in this kind of consensus, I think, but it was very short. There was some kind of split second. [pause] Could also be you know, I don't that they actually smiled. I remember the kid that was spinning a lot was smiling. He was smiling a lot. And he was looking in my eyes and I also because he was lying on the floor, and he was looking for me from upside down and the teacher was talking to me, and then I did like so I would see him from the right, you know, also upside down. I talked a little bit to him, and he was just smiling and happy. It was very cute. So maybe the one... the other child that was on the big platform that was also biting was actually smiling. And that's why I thought he was happy. But I guess you don't really in the moment you don't think about "oh, he's smiling. That's why I think He's happy. He's happy."

Interviewer 19:32

Yes, yes, of course. Yes, of course. I mean, you you sense that during the clapping. So just to recap. So during this like it was like second, they were like, like, communal clapping. So it was like a sense of like, togetherness. There was a communication between the people in the room. There was a very short moment. And the boy, that was like spinning, he was smiling and you looked at him and he smiled back. Okay.

Observer 1 20:02

Yeah, but that was not during the clapping more. I don't know if that was doing exactly more there were several instances when

Interviewer 20:08

Yes. Okay.

Observer 1 20:12

Because it was, I'm sure it was... I think it was dark during the clapping moment. And when he was on the ground, and he was talking to me, I remember that the lights were on. Okay. I mean, the long eye

contact that I had with that child [I think the clapping] moment that the lights were off. It would make more sense if it was, but I felt kind of like in the way there was something going on with the teachers too. Yeah. So it was very short.

Interviewer 20:46

So what's something on you mentioned that it was like a communication between the people in the room? How do you feel that communication?

Observer 1 20:56

What I thought in the moment was just because I've talked a lot to the one of the teachers before. And also seen in the when we've been on their music classes that they do that a lot. During the music, sessions, I think they've dance a lot with their hands. And they also clap. Or maybe not that they will have been clapping a lot that we have seen it. And we I think we've talked about it. But maybe it's been one of these things that we have seen. First, just a universal thing that when a child does that you're like, super happening.

Interviewer 21:39

But also, okay, so you thought in the moment you remember something that's it's related to... when they tend to dance with the hands and the clap, right? Instead of sociated with happiness, right?

Observer 1 21:53

Yes, I think so also because during this the previous sessions we've had we've been through video, they have recorded that they play music, and they are like dancing with the children, for example. There have been cases where I've seen one of them. Also, I think maybe the guy who was spinning around on the floor, I think it might have been him. That one the teachers were just, you know, they were dancing with their hands to the music that you know, just suddenly getting like... mesmerized almost, and just watching and being very happy. And like, focused... and caught up in that moment, obviously enjoying the teachers doing that. Okay, so you in the moment you thought of that moment, back to sort of knowledge that you had, they tend to like dance with the hands. But yeah, I guess to me, it's like, if they're doing things with their hands, they know that it's, you know, if the teachers do things with their head, it's like, I guess like, it's a positive thing. Yeah, the way I've interpreted it.

Interviewer 23:06

And if you for example, okay. So you have the knowledge and your reputation is like, positive. But let's go back to this moment when the kids are like, just clapping How did you feel? Actually? How was it for you?

Observer 1 23:29

I think it was just like, yes is working! I mean, like something... something was working, or something was going clearly going on there in the moment. And he was, I felt like this is some kind of, I don't know exactly what it means, but it's definitely an expression of something that they are feeling. And since two of them at least are clapping at the same time. At least two of them are feeling something or experiencing something that is worth to do the gesture.

Interviewer 24:05

How would you how would you define that something? Try

Observer 1 24:20

I mean, if I would, if I would guess now and this is like, of course, I have no idea.

Interviewer 24:23

Yeah, of course. Yeah,

Observer 1 24:25

I would just... I would just guess that, you know that since they don't move their legs so much. That they can be very, very expressive with their hands and communicate quite clearly with them. That's one of the ways they can actually actually express if they're feeling something strongly. They're also engaged you know, they do use your hands to some of them are like hitting the teachers little you know, or hitting themselves which I guess you know, of course, I interpreted as... [pause] the hitting yourself... I don't really know, of course, because I don't have the background to understand. Or the teacher I think it could just be like, you know, your child but, yeah, sorry, what was the question again? I derailed Oh, yes. How do I know that? It's a happy? Yeah. It's

Interviewer 25:27

like, how do you feel that happiness going on? You said that okay. So you said for example, of happiness was a sense of "Yes. it's working!"

Observer 1 25:39

Yeah, I think maybe because I'm thinking that, you know, they clap when they feel that there's maybe there's music or there's a rhythm, or there's something to clap to. Or it's like you clap after something that you like. Because I guess in general, that is what it means. It's either, like adjust you do to keep in rhythm, which means that maybe they perceived it as music, which was good, you know, because it's a pretty abstract sounds. But if they had some kind of sensation of this music to the very extent that I wanted to clap to it, it means that it feels a bit musical. Or if you clap you know you clap otherwise, after something it's usually like Affirmative. I'm also thinking of my nephew is one years old, and he's just starting to clap. And he's so happy when he does that. It's like it's the sign that he's like super excited. And then you know, feeling proud when... when he did that, and you can really see clearly... it's the pure sign of joy. I'm thinking now if there are any, you know, if there are any other situations where clapping could this really means... that you're not satisfied? [pause]

Interviewer 27:08

But they were satisfied?

Observer 1 27:11

I think so. It's also coordinated movement, which I guess is interesting also, because they have pretty limited movement that they can clap.

Interviewer 27:23

You said there were more than one kid clapping.

Observer 1 27:26

Yeah, I think there were two of them clapping almost at the same time or just after the other. But that can also be that I heard it and that like was looking at one of them. And then I heard another clap. Hopefully we will hear in the in the videos. But I think it was definitely it was not in the very other end of the room. I think it was the first string first and second strings. Probably it was those two could have been that it was one of the other ones and that suddenly clapped. But maybe I should ask the teachers what it means, you know when they clap? If it is... because I think if I'm just like trying to remember the video sessions we've been with them during the music, it seemed like when they're doing the dancing when they're listening to music.

Interviewer 28:31

So...you said that it was... so during the clapping... So you had a series of ideas connected to your knowledge about like, clapping you were reflecting also on which situation like clapping would mean something that's not positive. Right. So you were talking about this as well. And it was something like the sense of being together that you mentioned some time ago.

Observer 1 28:58

Yes. Exact some kind of togetherness, I guess.

Interviewer 29:01

Yeah. Could you try to describe how you felt that in the room? Like this togetherness? is a weird question.

Observer 1 29:15

Yeah, no, it's... I think there is of course, a lot in the dynamics because they are working in a group setting. So they are really in this group all the time. So of course, there's a lot of stuff going on, but maybe you know, if you come from an external perspective, you don't know what it means.

Interviewer 29:31

Yeah.

Observer 1 29:35

But I think definitely between between those two kids. There was there was some kind of togetherness to the very extent that the one that was moving around a lot and spinning you muscles, definitely he was like approaching the big platform that was vibrating but that also meant that he was approaching the other kid. So [pause] I'm trying to remember if I, you know, I first saw some in time, kind of clear interaction between them in or if it was more, you know, coming mostly from him because he was so so social. You he was, you know, you're looking at me he was talking to that teacher and then he...[pause] could also be that the you know, the one that was really playing really a lot in the beginning [pause] that he was actually interacting clearly with the teachers or the other kids without me really noticing it because I was, you know, just running around... when he was having a great time. I didn't see any, you

know, very clear togetherness with the girl that was in the very far end. Neither, I think on your side, where you were standing for on the other side.

Interviewer 31:15

Could you describe how was this non togetherness.

Observer 1 31:21

I think both of those cases where they were not so expressive with their body language. So in general, they were not moving a lot. Which meant that the teachers were playing for them on the strings. So they were pretty sitting pretty still. There was one time... maybe several, the one of them and I don't remember which one it was, was actually playing by herself. Maybe both of them... Not a lot. But like, in the end, on the floor, I think there was not much going on in general, for all the kids because they were also tired. I'm remembering it wrong. Now.

Interviewer 32:15

That's okay.

Observer 1 32:16

If it was actually that the one that was next to you was setting and then was playing a bit and was being a bit more interactive.

Interviewer 32:31

So what's happened? For example, let's go back to the moment when you realize that one of the kids... so there were two kids that weren't interactive. So think of one of them, like the one that is more more like present in your mind. And you see that the kid is not interacting, and that the technician, the pedagogue was playing with, with the string and the kid was doing nothing. How did you feel that moment?

Observer 1 33:10

And I can't try to focus on one of them, because they were kind of, I guess, I have the same emotional response or like interpretation to both the two girls that are moving so much. Well, one of them was funny. So the one that was close to you. I was not so worried about her. But she's she seemed to know what she was doing anyway. And I also listened to her conversation with the teacher when she said, I don't like it, it's too easy. Okay. And then I also read that that's what the teacher wrote. So once I'd heard that I'm like, she's just there doing its thing. She thinks this is too simple for her. And I, ... you know, it was more the other one that was lying on the floor, who was I knew was also hungry for her, I felt pretty bad, you know, that I'm like, she's sad. She wants to leave. If you're pushing it, she needs to take your snack now. And I was trying to like, you know, you can leave, you know, the want and then they were like, No, it's fine. We'll do it. But like when she was just lying down, and then the period and the [Observer3] was like, she's listening. She's listening to the music. I was like, she's basically dying. That's what's going on not but that's how I interpreted situation. And that made me of course, be like this. You know, I'm just this terrible scientist who's like, you know... not torturing kids, but like, you know, for my own purposes, forcing them to do this. So that was, of course a split second of not feeling

super great. Because of course, you want them to have a good time and I noticed it was always that they were all tired in the end. Everyone was tired apart from this little spinning guy. It was

Interviewer 34:59

The spinning guy like "Wooh"

Observer 1 35:02

Yeah, I was just like "I will just spin"

Interviewer 35:04

I would say I was a point where he was like, lying on his back, like looking at a light. Like, absolutely stuck. And I mentioned that [Observer 3] said no, but there was a point where the lights were off and he was still, like stuck looking at something.

Observer 1 35:22

Now he was lying a lot on his back. Yeah. But when I saw him spinning, I remember that I've seen him similar spinning in videos we've had with them. But I was thinking about the fact that he was like, really, he was really, you know, lying out his full body putting his full body on the floor. Looking now you know... looking at me that way. And then smiling. And then he was... I guess he cannot, he cannot move on. Like he is limited movement in his legs, but he could use his hand to pull himself where you want them. So I guess also, he was maybe different in a way because he he could also you know, if he felt I want to go there. He could do it. And he did it.

Interviewer 36:13

Yeah.

Observer 1 36:15

Whereas maybe the other ones couldn't do that. So the girl that was in the corner on the variable way back, you know, the one that I was most worried about, she seemed to be, you know, she couldn't move so much. I remember also a father videos, we've seen with her that that video that we had when they played the music that we made in playlist for them. She was not moving at all. And [Observer 2], and I looked at that. And we were both like, it's impossible for us to understand what's going on here. Basically, to, I guess both of us were just like, she's very sad. But then she was like that all the time. And I think that this, the teachers didn't seem to be very worried. So maybe it's just like, we cannot at all interpret her body language, or what she says.

Interviewer 37:05

So who was that girl? The one that was hungry?

Observer 1 37:08

Yes.

Interviewer 37:09

Okay.

Observer 1 37:10

The other one, in the beginning, when I was rolling her in, I was just like, Oh, my God, what have I have no idea what to do. I'm like, like, I never met them. And you know, I've never been hanging out with him. He works with anything like this. So. And also, we kind of promised in the, you know, the ethics that we wouldn't directly interact with them. Like, didn't want to like, you know, it didn't. It's tricky, of course, because, like, if it's like, if it's like, an average child, I would like know, maybe more do's and don'ts. But now it's just like, I don't make any mistake. So I was a bit worried about her. In the beginning. She was not moving a lot. And she was also hugging, which was pretty chill. That was my impression that was just like, I just put her there. She's like, Okay, I'm here. And she was playing.

Interviewer 38:01

I think at some point. Yeah, I was thinking, it's very interesting. What [Observer 3] said about, like this girl that's supposed to be like, sad. And she said, totally the opposite. And then she also said that, yeah, I'm going a little bit outside of [the interview] she what's also saying that... I think I said, "Yeah, it's kind of problematic when one sort of impose the kids to do things." And she mentioned... it's like "Yeah, but it's okay that they are uncomfortable. Like, sometimes it's like, it's a way of learning because they are like..."

Observer 1 38:45

so the kids she thinks it's like, it's not...

Interviewer 38:47

it's not a problem, because

Observer 1 38:49

morally corrupt to like, [inaudible].

Interviewer 38:52

Yeah, it's not like a terrible discomfort, but it's more like a little bit of discomfort is not a bad thing is a learning experience.

Observer 1 38:59

Yeah, that's interesting. Maybe it's true, because it's like, of course, in one way, that's also because she's worked a lot with them. She's just like, they're just like any other kids?

Interviewer 39:08

Yes, of course.

Observer 1 39:09

So it's like, and with any other child, you wouldn't be like, I will not tell you what to do. Hmm.

Interviewer 39:19

Yeah.

Observer 1 39:22

But of course, that's a lot how I felt, you know, in this process, and also when, you know, the especially in the end when they were tired, I, you know, a part of me felt really bad. Really, really bad. And that's because I'm like, it's it was too long. They were all tired. Yeah.

Interviewer 39:43

And you felt like a terrible scientist.

Observer 1 39:45

I mean, I felt like you're just like, it's and I didn't feel like super terrible, but I felt a bit like I could it was even though I don't know how to... Well, I guess they weren't just not moving. Maybe it was actually that this guy that was so happy in the beginning. He was not moving at all. He was not saying, you know, he was not showing strongly or like screaming or like indicating, I guess, to the teacher that he wanted out. But he's behavior it had completely changed in relation to how he was exactly when he came when he was just like having a great time playing the string, like, you know, making the sounds like, okay, he's just doing his own thing. The lights are not even off, everything's working so well. And then he was just sitting next to the string.

Interviewer 40:34

So when he was sitting next to the string, he was still you said, right? Yes. So and he was leaning towards the string as well, at some point, and then is when he bites like a string, right? Yeah,

Observer 1 40:50

but that was earlier. I think it was not when he was on the floor, when he was tired and didn't know. What might have been that he tried again, in the end, I don't really remember.

Interviewer 41:03

Yeah, sure. There were like, four kids, it's hard to remember all the details. And that's fine, too. I mean,

Observer 1 41:11

I just remember that, you know, I have this visual memory of like him being there on the floor, and then just, it's dark. So I don't see so much. And I'm just seeing that there's this dark shape next to the string and nothing is happening. And then I thought, well, that's we must be really tired.

Interviewer 41:27

You know, it would be interesting. So what I'm getting here is like, we have lots of moments. Normally, we just pick one thing. I mean, like, for example, the clapping, and we can expand the clapping, sort of like theorize around just one second clapping. And we can have an interview about like physical clapping. But something that I'm getting out of this is it would be very interesting to... Okay, so the disagreements between like the person who has experience and also there are like different interpretations. I think it would be interesting to have a look at the video of the kid that was leaning towards like, because I was filming him. And I remember I also thought okay, he's now yeah, actually, you were filming? Yes. Yeah. So I thought, Oh, he's like, perhaps not very comfortable, because I'm

filming. But then I notice, okay, he was leaning towards like the string and he was like, biting it was like, sort of like, chewing it, perhaps or licking it, which to me, it responds to a certain type of interaction. So it would be interesting to see his facial expression to notice if he was, in fact trying to connect with the vibration. It would be interesting

Observer 1 42:38

Maybe he wanted to feel it

Interviewer 42:39

wanted to feel it. Exactly. There was something there and also check like the body maps.

Observer 1 42:45

That's true that's what he said. Yeah, I didn't I didn't look at it yet.

Interviewer 42:48

That would be interesting, because then it would be the case that we have two kids, that got still because they want to feel that vibration. So they were attentive, they were listening through their bodies. Yeah, that would be very interesting.

Observer 1 43:00

I thought about that a little bit, too, that also some, you know, that. I'm like, Are they still because they're tired? Or they are... it's it's also like, it could also be a certain point. I was thinking they are still now but they are not showing that they are not happy or that they exactly, yeah, they wouldn't react or they just like, this is fine. I'm just listening. And then we're tired. So I won't do so much for I'm totally chill. We're just sitting here. Yeah, feeling this.

Interviewer 43:23

We can check that out because [Observer 3] was really like, she was really sort of clear. It's like this girl with the red hair. She was very happy. I mean, she described when she asked... Well, she was just before the last experience that light was on and she was like making noise, hungry, like Grumpy. Like she said, she was making her grumpy noises. So then when they turn the lights off, and she was like lying on the ground, she noticed she was very happy. And we were saying that she was like, sad. She was very happy, like attentive, closing the eyes, opening the eyes, like relaxed, like this sort of attitude. And then when the light went on, and she was asked, Where did you feel the vibrations? She said face and back was exactly the places where she was lying on.

Observer 1 44:14

So she was saying that? Yes.

Interviewer 44:16

And actually, when the lights went on, it made a little bit of like some grumpy noises again. And it was like [Observer 3] said there was like "aghh", this kind of thing. Yeah, we're talking Okay. It's like teenagers, you know? "Agggghh. Blahh... Too many questions." Okay. And yeah, she was very happy to watch this correspondence between what she saw and the actual like data that they got to the cards.

So it would be interesting. So what I'm getting from this, your interview would be interesting to see if the guy that was leaning towards was he relaxed? So to ask for example, the educators what they think.

Observer 1 44:56

yeah, like, was he super tired and like the Like getting the band, why was he not moving? Yeah. You see that the progression like, okay, he was obviously moving a lot at certain times. And then so in some times, he was just saying, Yeah, we're doing other things,

Interviewer 45:13

but they weren't reacting against it.

Observer 1 45:17

But yeah, that's

Interviewer 45:20

like how they were actually feeling... especially, especially during the last part, interact, because the last was different. Also, like the kid that was spinning, there was something going on there. Like, he was trying to perceive, like, follow like this more powerful sort of sensation. So if that seems to be like the case, so the kids were like, connecting very nicely with this more like, okay, but the second one was, so perhaps they were actively like trying to connect with the vibrations, even though it doesn't look evident to us.

Observer 1 45:55

Yeah, that's the thing, right? You know, you just look at it, and you don't know what exactly they are feeling. So it could be that they were just listening to their body, [inaudible].

Interviewer 46:06

But that's, that's amazing. That's a way of interaction, and listening attentively. Through the body. Yeah,

Observer 1 46:12

that's one thing we thought about a lot when we were like, how do we make the vibrations because we were going back and forth. And like either, we have something continuous. So there's this ambient thing in the in the displayed all the time when there's haptics so that if they want to, they can stop and just listen and feel it? Because we didn't want to end up in a situation where it's only the interaction with the string? Because then we're like, how are we going to know? You know, because if you only play once done, you can say it's not really they didn't feel much haptics. Yeah. But at the same time, then you introduce other you know, these things like you don't know if they don't play, because they don't like the sounds and the vibrations when you're playing? Or if it's just that they are just listening.

Interviewer 47:02

Yeah, we cannot didn't realize, but I think that my this testimony was like, impression on the things was like, it's gonna be like, a little key to sort of understand how the other kids were interacting, I suspect.

Observer 1 47:19

Yeah, like, you have to have the perspective. Yeah. And we have also, we haven't tested it with anyone else. There were just a bunch of kids that came in afterwards. And we didn't see what they did. They just ran through pretty quickly. But there were some grownups that came in. And they were acting very funny in comparison to what people usually do, or I don't know if it was because they were Swedish and polite. Usually, people come and they at least touch the strings. But they were just going in, like, always supposed to look like this. They didn't touch anything now. So I guess something about it now, because probably there is this, this ambient thing that you feel that you more get the maybe it's maybe just invites to listening?

Interviewer 48:03

Interesting.

Observer 1 48:04

I don't know. We will have to, you know, sit there and check what people are spontaneously doing. That's the kids played though. I think that maybe? I don't know. I don't know if it's received more as an installation than like, an instrument.

Interviewer 48:19

Haha, ha, that's so yeah.

Observer 1 48:23

I hope I managed to say any something useful?

Interviewer 48:26

Yes. I mean, they were debriefing. And I think that yes, absolutely.

Observer 1 48:30

was fine. Yeah, I didn't go into super much emotional detail, no problems, small experience,

Interviewer 48:35

no problem. I think that this was very useful, because it was more like a sort of reflective listening. micro phenomenological I interview, but I think it was useful because we gave lots of different like, clues, or the kids were interacting, and also your perceptions on how they were reacting that seemed to be different to what [Observer 3] was saying, for example. It's interesting. I mean, there's something there. I don't know the fact that you know, this, that the kid was like, looking like, you know, I think all these things are interesting to like, verify they were trying to feel they were inactive because they were trying to listen, that would be super interesting.

Observer 1 49:21

Maybe we should ask, you know, we should ask maybe the teacher was a great thing that they were Yes, sure. Where they actually when they were not playing was it because they were listening wasn't because they just didn't like it that either. No.

Interviewer 49:41

Which could be the case of yeah,

Observer 1 49:43

Probably changed throughout also. But it's very interesting that [Observer 3] said that she was happy in the end because I was like so worried. But I also but [Observer 3] also insisted, because I was like, you can allow this fine if you don't want to, you know, she can go out and have a snack. You know, it's totally fine. And she was like, no, no, don't do it. It's fine. Just Just a couple more minutes. She was really insisting and I was just like, I guess she knows what she's doing. So maybe she understood also that like, if if she just gets to start again, she's gonna be happy, you know? Yeah, maybe she was it was just that.

Interviewer 50:13

Yeah, she was like oh no, she was totally into it. She was very happy

Observer 1 50:19

it's very Yeah, maybe you know, maybe me something completely different. Do I stop here?

Interviewer 50:25

Yeah, sure. clapping clapping Yes, like